

“ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN BORDER CONTROL: OPPORTUNITY OR THREAT? AN ANALYSIS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PRACTICES IN CONTROLLING BORDER”

Mr. Ateeq Javed¹, Prof. Dr. Rashid Aftab², Dr. Ismail Adaramola Abdul Azeez³

¹Officer in Border Management/Immigration Wing of FIA-Pakistan

^{2,3}Riphah Institute of Public Policy, Riphah International University

¹ateeqjaved@aol.com, ²rashid.aftab@riphah.edu.pk, ³ismail.adaramola@riphah.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17696082>

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence (AI), Surveillance System, Migration Policy, Ethical Artificial Intelligence, Human Rights, Security Technology and Algorithmic Decision-making

Article History

Received: 01 October 2025

Accepted: 10 November 2025

Published: 24 November 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Prof. Dr. Rashid Aftab

Abstract

This thesis focuses on the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in border control, discussing the idea of whether it is an opportunity or a threat to state security, governance, and human rights. The paper follows the historical development of border security, starting with primitive physical barriers as the primitive form of border security, to the modern surveillance systems based on AI, which points to the technological, ethical, and political sides of dealing with border security today. The study uses a literature review to come up with major themes such as the efficiency of operations, ethical and human rights issues, governance gaps, impact on the society and global differences in the use of AI. The results show that AI boosts the efficiency, accuracy, and predictive ability of the border control activity greatly, allowing to identify the risks in real-time, evaluate them, and improve the management of the migration. All the advantages, however, come at the cost of significant risks associated with algorithmic bias, breaching privacy, dehumanization of migrants, and reduced transparency and accountability. The two-sided character of AI represents a radical prospect of changing the border to seem more modern and also a threat to the democratic control and human rights. The paper concludes that implementation of AI in border management should be successful with strong ethical principles on the one hand, to achieve the balance between the security goals and the respect of the personal rights through effective human control and transparency, as well as international collaboration. The study will add to the discussion of AI in border governance by critically commenting on how it operates, ethically, and in the society. It underlines that borders systems that are operated by AI require interdisciplinary strategies and policy interventions that would help to make them instruments of protection and not control.

INTRODUCTION

In the Political Science, the State refers to a sovereign political community that has permanent population, defined territory, established government and that has the ability to have relations with other states. Compared to the other two, Max

Weber reknownly added to the statement that the state is “the human community that successfully claims the monopoly of the legitimate use of physical force within a given territory”. The state is, therefore, the ultimate legal, political authority who structures

society, law enforcement, order maintenance and also reflects the will of the masses.

The state plays a central role in ensuring that there is social order, security, and protection of the rights of the citizens. In the absence of a central authority, the society would lack order, fighting and insecurity. The state creates and implements laws, provides justice and governs social, political and economic relations. The state holds a sense of stability through its institutions, which include judiciary, bureaucracy, legislature, and executive as these ensure stability and provide the conditions in which human flourishing can occur. It also secures people against domestic and foreign (war, civil conflict) threats.

Moreover, the state is an important stakeholder in social welfare, economic and nation-building. It offers the basic services of education, health, infrastructures as well as economic control as the key player to collective development. The state also acts on behalf of its people in the international system; negotiating treaties, encouraging cooperation and safeguarding national interests. The state is an essential element in contemporary political existence since it is where social identities are formed, communal welfare is encouraged, and a political framework through which people can engage in democracy and make their decisions as a group.

Similarly, state territory protection has been one of the characteristic aspects of political organization since the beginning of humanity. During the primitive period, the primitive societies existed in the form of tribes and clans whose existence was based on protecting their resources, people and settlements against external aggression. Protection methods were mostly natural and collective in nature, rivers, mountains, thick forests and deserts served as a natural barrier to groups and prevented invasions. Societies constructed boundaries of their territories based on traditional and verbal concepts and determined areas of control and membership. Some of the defense techniques were armed watch groups, primitive weapons such as spears and bows and joint vigilance. These were just the infantile steps towards what would later be incarnated into the contemporary notion of borders.

With the increase in the complexity of the forms of governance in the societies, the techniques of protection of the territories also developed. The

protection became a formalized role of the state with the emergence of ancient civilizations like Mesopotamia, Egypt, Persia, China and the Indus Valley. These civilizations constructed walls, fortifications and outposts to guard trading routes and to prevent invasions. The Great Wall of China was constructed and deepened throughout centuries, which may be viewed as the struggle of the early state to utilize infrastructure as a geopolitical defense tool. The city walls and the fortification of the borders were used in Mesopotamia and ancient Egypt to ensure the safety of the citizens, as well as to declare power, sovereignty, and organized rule of the kingdom. The ancient Romans had advanced border mechanisms referred to as *limes* that incorporated roads, watchtowers, and garrisons that monitored communication and imposed imperial control. These inventions marked a great advancement of natural borders which were passive to active structures of defence which were created by man.

Fortification and the power over land became closely connected with feudalism and the royal authority of the medieval period. The key frontiers were provided with castles, fortresses and military posts that had to protect and monitor. Borders were not demarcated always and acted as the sphere of influence of rival powers. As the centralized kingdoms increasingly developed, and the system of the nation-state finally emerged in Europe, especially after the Treaty of Westphalia (1648), the idea of a border came to be established as a legal and political frontier. Borders also became a symbol of state sovereignty where the governing of one state and the other started. The necessity to protect these borders turned into a national pride and necessity.

The industrial and technological revolutions in the modern world changed the border protection. Firearms, telegraphy, radar and aerial surveillance were invented, which enhanced the ability of a state to notice and fend off threats. The 20th century experienced the most remarkable growth in the borders management system, the system of custom checkpoints, the system of immigration control and the system of passport verification, that is, the dual ambitions of the state to provide security and control. The Cold War also led to the tightening of the border checks through the establishment of militarized borders, and most notably the Berlin wall

which symbolized the ideological boundary between the East and the West. The focus was no longer on the protection of the territory, but on the movement control which included not only the military threat but also the migration, smuggling and the terrorist.

The post-9/11 era brought in a new era of international security awareness and as a result, the controls along the borders have been tight and the use of digital technology has been incorporated. States started adopting biometric systems, electronic passports, and surveillance networks as a part of their border management regimes. Databases were interconnected, and traveler information could be shared across national borders. Nevertheless, the surge in international movement and transnational risks of terrorism and organized crime required more rapid and smarter detection and response mechanisms.

The 21st century has transformed the borders protection landscape after Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration. Facial recognition, predictive analytics, data mining, and machine learning AI technologies are implemented to pr

ocess huge volumes of data on-the-fly. ABC systems like e-gates at airports are automated systems that apply AI to identify people, detect suspicious activity, and facilitate processing. Remote border areas are covered by surveillance drones with computer vision and predictive algorithms to analyze travel patterns and indicate risky individuals. Such systems provide the states with the most effective and efficient capabilities to secure the borders, which is assured to be more accurate, cost-cutting, and quicker in giving a decision.

Nonetheless, the ethical, legal, and social issue of AI integration into border protection is deeply problematic. Although AI enhances efficiency and surveillance power, AI also creates the dangers of algorithmic bias, intrusion of privacy, misuse of data, and lack of accountability. Opacity of AI systems may be a challenge in guaranteeing fairness or challenging automated decisions, especially against migrants and asylum-seekers whose privileges are already dubious. Besides, the application of predictive analytics in border security also endangers the change of borders into a territory of constant surveillance, where citizens are profiled not based on their actions but

on their hypotheses as to what algorithms can imagine they might do.

In this way, the development of the protection systems at the border since ancient times, consisting of primordial natural barriers and modern digital barriers based on AI, provides a spectrum on which the human search of security and control is based. Every stage is indicative of technology, politics, and morality of its era. In the modern world, where states adopt AI to protect their borders, one of the most pressing questions is an answer to the following: can technology really become the guarantee of security without undermining human dignity and rights? The solution lies in the way the societies develop the governance mechanisms to make sure that AI is the instrument of protection rather than domination and that the counterbalance between the sovereignty and freedom of humans is maintained in the era of intelligent boundaries.

Problem Statement

The growing number of applications of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) in border security has reshaped the old ways of ensuring state security and security by posing both immense opportunities and serious threats. Although AI is expected to improve the security effectiveness, facilitate identification procedures as well as decrease human error, it also provokes the complicated issues connected to privacy, accountability, discrimination, and human rights. The world is quickly embracing AI-driven systems, including biometric databases, facial recognition, and predictive analytics; they are not accompanied by proper legal frameworks or clear mechanisms of oversight. Such rapid advancement in technology poses the threat of going faster than ethical

and regulatory controls, and causing the possibility of misusing personal data, algorithmic discrimination, and undermining basic civil rights.

The key issue is that AI is a twofold phenomenon in border management: it is both a strategic asset and a possible danger. It reinforces the power of a nation-state and its capacity to combat threats on the one hand, and on the other, it can become institutionalized surveillance, discrimination, and digital exclusion in a country, particularly among migrants and vulnerable groups. Moreover, the

absence of international standards and interoperability frameworks also adds to the inconsistency of a practice and the absence of equal protection of rights among jurisdictions. The legal responsibility to the rights violation is made complicated by the ambiguity of who is supposed to be held accountable, and therefore, is it the governments, technology vendors or automated systems.

Thus, the presented research aims to discuss the possibilities and risks of AI in border control critically, as there is an immediate necessity to find the golden mean between technological innovation and the ethical control of the situation. The research question focuses on getting information about whether the use of AI in border protection can increase security without disrupting the principles of democracy, human rights, and international justice.

Research Questions

1. What AI technologies are presently deployed in border control, and how are they operationally implemented?
2. What evidence exists of the usefulness, reliability and dependability of AI systems at the border?
3. What impact does AI implementation have on major fundamental rights, including privacy, non-discrimination, and the right to seek asylum?
4. Which governance, legal, and technical controls can minimize risks without harming benefits?

Research Objectives:

1. To map the current AI-based tools in border management.
2. To analyze case studies to demonstrate the way AI is implemented in practice.
3. To assess the advantages and disadvantages in comparison to empirical research and policy papers.
4. To suggest/propose a composite system of governance in the field of an ethical use of AI in border control.

Research Significance

This research is important because it contributes to the analysis of a challenging interaction between

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and border control in the framework of contemporary governance, security, and human rights. Through critical analysis of the operational capabilities of AI, its ethical effects, as well as its effects on society, this study can be instrumental in helping policy makers, border management representatives, and researchers to discover a balance between technological innovation and ethical accountability. To begin with, the study emphasizes the effectiveness of AI in streamlining borders, enhancing threat detection, and advancing the goals of national security, which may be of great value to governments that implement AI technologies. Secondly, it highlights the possible harm of the deployment of AI, such as the existence of algorithmic bias, breach of privacy, and undermining civil liberties, thus informing the creation of ethical and legal systems. Thirdly, the investigation of the global differences in the adoption and governance of AI adds to the discourse of global collaboration, establishment of standards, and fair usage of technologies. In the end, this study can offer a basis of evidence-based policy, interdisciplinary research, and ethical deployment of AI in border security management to ensure that technological progress will enhance security without compromising human rights and democratic principles.

Literature Review

The body of literature on Artificial Intelligence (AI) in border control proves the dynamism between technology, state security, human rights, and governance. With increased global migration and the development of transnational threats, the governments have increasingly turned to AI-based systems to streamline the efficiency, speed, and accuracy of the border management process. Academic scholarship and policy discussion, however, demonstrate that this technological change is associated with the benefits of operations, as well as the difficulties with ethical, legal, and political issues. This chapter includes a thorough overview of the literature that was published up to date.

The alteration of the physical borders into the digital ones has changed the approaches of the state's surveillance and control. Biometric identification, automated facial recognition, predictive analytics,

and behavioral analysis are AI-driven systems that have become a common set of tools in contemporary border management. The authors indicate that the adoption of these technologies has increased the real-time validation and reduced human error, especially at high-volume border points such as airports and seaports (Pavone & Degli, 2021). The European Union Smart Borders Initiative, the Biometric Entry/Exit Program of the United States, and the SmartGate system of Australia are the best examples of how the governments are exploring AI to improve the processing of migration and better security.

In addition, machine learning algorithms have become useful in identifying suspicious migration patterns, fake documents, and even threats by making predictions. According to Gonzalez et al. (2020), the analytical capabilities of AI allow authorities to recognize risks before they become real, which is a paradigm shift of reactive management of the border to proactive one. Nevertheless, as revealed by Buolamwini and Gebru (2018), there is one serious flaw in this, namely the issue of racial and gender prejudice in AI recognition systems, which leads to false identifications of minorities being even higher. Such errors, coupled with the environmental conditions such as lighting or camera angle, question the concept of AI infallibility. Dencik and Hintz (2022) also warn that the automation of border screening can lead to the desensitization of human judgment and create the atmosphere in which responsibility becomes obsolete under the name of machine rulings.

When the AI is applied in border control, it tends to be ahead of the regulation of its use, creating the asymmetry of governance between technology and law. As Molnar (2021) and Hayes and Vermeulen (2022) explain, the interoperability systems of the European Union, including the Entry/Exit System (EES), Visa Information System (VIS), and ETIAS, facilitate the data exchange between national borders to a seamless flow. Although these systems increase the capacity of the operation, they also pose some concerns regarding centralization of data, cross-border privacy and jurisdiction. Here, the behavioral risk profiling tools used by the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) and Customs and Border Protection (CBP) in the United States are based on

AI and are commonly shrouded in national security exemptions that remain largely non-transparent.

The studies of governance highlight the shortage of accountability and independent supervision of the algorithms. Doyle (2020) and Taylor (2022) emphasize that the majority of nations have not been building extensive models of algorithmic auditing or transparency to the population. The absence of ethical protection surrounding the usage of AI tools enables their fast growth without proper governance measures. This unequal balance can threaten the democratic control and the emergence of what Zuboff (2019) describes as the surveillance capitalism, where information turns into a commodity and a tool of control. Technical regulations are therefore not enough to govern the areas of AI power, but rather to engage in a wider political and ethical debate on the extent of AI power in state security apparatus.

The issues of AI in the management of the border have revolved around ethical debate based on privacy, fairness, and human rights. Delegating security functions to algorithms is an aspect that poses basic questions of human discretion erosion when making life and liberty decisions. Klonick (2021) concludes that replacing the human empathy with the computational logic may result in moral distancing, where border officials will be a mere executor of decisions made by machines. Equally, Mann and Daly (2019) emphasize that the rationality of AI data can be incompatible with the humanitarian aspect since efficiency is prioritized over compassion.

Lawwise, data protection regulations like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of EU have a legal framework on consent, transparency, and minimization of data. However, the border control agencies are often not subjected to such responsibilities in the name of national security. This puts a grey zone where large volume of personal information is handled without their own consent or any definite retention boundaries. According to Taylor (2022), accountability is further exacerbated by the fact that machine learning models are often opaque, also known as the black box problem, and authorities as well as those who are being impacted by the decisions made in machine learning do not

understand the manner in which those decisions are made.

Further, the ethical application of AI is not limited to the privacy of data but also the question of inclusivity and justice. The structural disadvantage of migrants and asylum seekers is generated by algorithmic bias and lack of representativeness in data sets and the lack of mechanisms of appeal. Veale and Binns (2017) emphasize that the issues of fairness in AI are technical, ethical, and require openness, training data diversity, and participatory system design.

In addition to the technical and legal issues, critical security and political theory scholars can provide more information on the power relation inherent in AI-assisted border systems. According to Amoore (2020) and Bellanova (2021), predictive surveillance changes the idea of the border as being a physical line into a digital ecosystem of networks. People are not divided in terms of their citizenship or place of residence but according to their data profiles and algorithmic risk scores. This change in the nature of borders, that is, the replacement of the territorial borders by the informational ones is an indication of a new digital sovereignty, in which it does not govern the territorial borders, but manages the data level.

The postcolonial perspective on AI in border management focus by Eubanks (2018) and Zureik (2021) shows that AI contributes to the existence of global disparities. It is the richer states that use high-tech surveillance mechanisms that are unproportionately used against migrants in the poorer or conflict-ridden countries. This supports pre-established hierarchies and justifies exclusionary practices. According to Leese (2020), the author refers to this phenomenon as the technological militarization of borders when humanitarian migration has been redefined as a crises in the security situation, which has resulted in the naturalization of surveillance at all times.

Critical theory also provides AI boundaries to the wider socio-political patterns: such as digital authoritarianism and securitization of the state. The increased reliance on predictive algorithms does not only expand the surveillance of states but also transfers the moral responsibility of violence on the borders to the machine. According to Bigo (2022), such technological mediation enables the

governments to engage in aggressive migration control and reduce the apparent human responsibility.

The cross-regional empirical research demonstrates that AI is a controversial topic in border control. Efforts such as the EU-LISA database and AI-based risk assessment systems by Frontex have helped to increase the efficiency of operations in the European Union, but were criticized due to the lack of transparency, as well as the possible misuse of data. The application of automated facial recognition in airports and drone overflights of the Mexican border by CBP has become a constitutional issue in the United States in terms of the Fourth Amendment and racial profiling (Snow, 2021). In Australia, AI in immigration decision-making resulted in greater efficiency but also caused legal debate on the question of the algorithm bias and false deportations (Liu, 2022). These geographic differences show that the influence of AI is not only determined by technology, but also by the local government and political culture, and the customs of civil rights.

Research Gaps

Even with the growing literature on the issues, there are still major gaps in knowledge. The available empirical data that analyzes the real success of AI, its accuracy, and its long-term effects on the migration policy are limited. The current literature does not commonly assess the practical usefulness and precision of AI in border operations and creates a significant gap in the knowledge of the practical results.

Research Methodology

The research has a qualitative and comparative case study design with the assistance of the content analysis of the policy documents, technical reports, scholarly literature, news articles, and court decisions. The main data collections are the agency reports and documents that face the public; the secondary ones are scholarly articles and civil society evaluations.

The process of the analysis was:

1. Systematic gathering of reports, white papers and peer reviewed studies on the use of AI in border control.

2. Themes and coding in order to determine recurring benefits, harms, and governance practices.
3. Comparative analysis of the differences in the legal structures, the control system, and the reported cases.

Limitations: this study utilizes open-source content and is therefore likely to fail in revealing operational details that are classified. In addition, the scope of the evaluation of system performance was not quantitative because the access to raw technical metrics was not extensive.

Findings and Discussion

The chapter highlights the results of the study concerning the Artificial Intelligence (AI) in border control and whether its application can be viewed as a chance or a danger to global security, governance, and human rights. The analysis is based on the synthesis of the information presented in policy documents, empirical research, and theoretical viewpoints, which help to identify major trends, patterns, and implications of AI use in border control. The debate is divided into thematic areas: efficiency and operational effectiveness, ethical and human rights issues, societal and political issues, and the general conclusion on AI as both an opportunity and a threat.

Theme 01: Operational Effectiveness and efficiency.

The research concludes that AI has improved the efficiency of border management operations to a large extent as it has automated the processes of identity verification, document screening, and threat detection. Facial recognition, fingerprint and behavioral analytics are systems that minimize human error and manual work. One case in point, the border kiosks sensed with AI have been reported to be faster and more efficient in identifying fake documents at the airports. The prediction of activities is also possible with AI tools, turning suspicious traveling patterns and transnational migration into mistakes observed before any event has taken place.

These results prove that AI is a part of strategic modernization of border management. It facilitates restrictions between real-time information gathering

among a multiplicity of agencies and jurisdictions, whereby states may organize the reaction to the unlawful movement, terrorism, and transnational criminal activities. Nonetheless, the research also shows that efficiency gains are also costly. The excessive usage of the AI systems can lead to the occurrence of technological addiction because human officers become mere enforcers, instead of decision-makers. This brings about issues of institutional resilience, which is whether the border systems can work in the event of AI system failure or malfunction.

Theme 02: Ethical and Human Rights Considerations

The study sheds light on the prevalent doubts about the ethics of AI application in managing the border. The results indicate that AI technologies are efficient but tend to do so at the prejudice of privacy, fairness, and the dignity of people. Such gathering and use of biometric and personal information without prior authorization contradicts the principles of the international human rights, such as the right to privacy, which is provided in the Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR).

Besides, the problem of algorithmic bias continues to be one of the most urgent ones detected. The available empirical data shows that AI-driven facial recognition and risk assessment systems often tend to misidentify members of a minority or marginalized group. These inaccuracies might result in unfair detention, deportation, or rejection, particularly of people of color and asylum seekers.

The other important conclusion is concerned with dehumanization of border processes. AI implementation makes the interaction of migrants and officials less human-centered and more focused on a computer-assisted decision-making process. This automation has the potential to dehumanize the migration processes, and turn humanitarian interactions into data operations. Ethical issues, thus, do not concern technological bias only but the moral and emotional aspect of the border control.

Theme 03: Societal and Political Implications

In addition to operational and legal aspects, the conclusions show the far-reaching societal and political consequences of the integration of AI in

border control. The application of AI technologies is also related to the securitization of the migration process in which human movement is viewed as a threat instead of a natural social phenomenon. The change has instilled a sense of fear of migrants in the minds of the people and has justified the restrictive and exclusionary policies.

Moreover, the research concludes that AI solidifies inequalities in the world between developed and less developed countries. The rich nations are able to afford highly advanced technologies at the border, whereas the poor countries can turn into the test subjects when it comes to AI prototypes created by corporations or even foreign governments. This interaction increases geopolitical inequality and continues the marginalization of the vulnerable groups.

The results further indicate that AI surveillance is a factor that makes digital authoritarianism be normalized, in which citizens and non-citizens are constantly monitored. With increasing range of state surveillance through predictive algorithms, a distinction between domestic and international surveillance is diminished. This is a threat to democracy and civil freedoms, since unrestricted AI technologies can be used to support mass surveillance even outside border areas.

Theme 04: Artificial Intelligence (AI) as an Opportunity and a Threat

The general discussion shows that AI in border control represents both an enormous opportunity and a great threat. Being an opportunity, it increases efficiency, national security and allows making decisions based on the data, which is capable of preventing criminal operations and human trafficking. The fact that AI can handle high volumes of information within a short time enables states to react promptly to the transnational threat, making the border control more adaptive and smarter.

On the other hand, AI is a serious ethical, legal, and societal threat. It causes a danger of institutionalizing discrimination, losing privacy, and allowing disproportionate surveillance in the name of safety. AI systems can turn out to be the instruments of discrimination and political control instead of safety without the appropriate level of control. The state of security and liberty is therefore delicate.

Conclusion

The results of this paper indicate that the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in border control is at the boundary between innovation and ethical issues. On the one hand, AI technologies have increased the efficiency, accuracy, and responsiveness of the process of managing the border dramatically. Robotic identity checks, predictive analytics and data-driven surveillance have helped states to facilitate the immigration process and more efficiently react to transnational dangers. These innovations are a significant technological breakthrough in the intensification of world border control. Nonetheless, the study also illustrates that AI advantages are associated with massive ethical and governance issues. Biometric data and opaque algorithms as well as predictive profiling have become a significant challenge to the privacy of individuals and human dignity. Moreover, the results of algorithmic biases have been discriminatory, especially towards minority groups and asylum seekers, which contradicts the principles of fairness and justice. The absence of multilateral laws and systems of accountability has facilitated unmitigated application of AI in the framework of national security discourses. Thus, AI is efficient and safe but, at the same time, it can lead to the infestation of digital authoritarianism and the legalization of inequality. Ultimately, the implementation of AI in border control is a game changer as well as a significant threat. It could make border security and administration more effective, but without strong ethical protection and governance systems, it is likely to undermine basic human rights. The future of AI in this area should thus be steered by the pledge of transparency, inclusivity, and governance based on people and make sure that the technological development is at the service of humanity and not its master.

Recommendations

1. Ethical principles should be embraced by governments and international bodies in the application of AI in border control, which should focus on fairness, accountability, and transparency. Such frameworks ought to be legally enforceable as opposed to being advisory.

2. Migration and border screening AI systems should be capable of being explained and audited. The access to the principles of algorithm design and the control by independent experts should be required so as to avoid abuse.
3. Artificial intelligence can be used to supplement human judgement and not to substitute it. The final decision making power should remain with the border officials to prevent accountability and empathy failure in the enforcement.
4. There should be clear policies regarding the data collection, storage and sharing. The collection of biometric and personal data should be performed with an informed consent and with high standards of data protection.
5. Discrimination in AI systems should be reduced with the help of regular audits and a variety of data training sets. Hidden biases can be tackled by inclusion of multidisciplinary teams, particularly ethicists, sociologists, and human rights gurus.
6. The international governance of AI at the borders should be supported by multilateral institutions like the UN and IOM to enable worldwide discussion and establish a standard of ethical practice that all states would follow.
7. Digital literacy, ethics, and human rights training ought to be incorporated in the border personnel training programs to promote a responsible application of AI tools.
8. The use of AI systems in border operations should be monitored and evaluated by independent regulatory bodies to ensure that AI systems comply with ethical standards.
9. Lastly, AI border systems should maintain humanitarian principles and should treat migrants and refugees with dignity, compassion, and fairness.

Final Reflection

The introduction of AI into the border management can be viewed as the reflection of the larger conflict between technological development and moral accountability. It lacks as a technical or administrative problem, it is a moral challenge. The way out is to moderate innovation and

accountability, where AI-driven security does not contradict the freedom of humans. The AI age requires the use of smarter technologies and wiser institutions - the ones that promote justice, equality, and the sacred dignity of every person who crosses a border.

Limitations and Future research.

This thesis was based on the open-source documentation and was therefore not able to encompass the practices that are classified. Further studies ought to make empirical performance assessments utilizing audit records, examine the long-run sociopolitical effects of biometric regimes on cross-border societies, and examine participatory governance frameworks that consider the affected groups.

REFERENCES

- Al-Thani, M. G. (2025). AI on the frontlines: Transforming border security in the fight against drug and arms smuggling. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 8(4), 1928-1945. <https://doi.org/10.53894/ijirss.v8i4.8277>
- Belderbos, H. (2025, January 16). *AI for border control speed and security*. Open Access Government. <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/ai-for-broader-control-speed-and-security/187217/>
- Benton, L., & Clulow, A. (2017). Introduction: The Long, Strange History of Protection. In *Cambridge University Press eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108283595.001>
- Bigo, D. (2014). The (in)securitization practices of the three universes of EU border control: Military/Navy - border guards/police - database analysts. *Security Dialogue*, 45(3), 209-225. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0967010614530459>
- Buolamwini, J., & Gebru, T. (2018, January 21). *Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification*. PMLR. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/buolamwini18a.html>
- Business Case Studies. (2025, March 18). *The State (Origins, Functions, Sovereignty)*. <https://businesscasestudies.co.uk/the-state-origins-functions-sovereignty/>

- Crossref, & Amoores, L. (2022). *Cloud Ethics: Algorithms and the Attributes of Ourselves and Others*. Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9781478009276>
- Eklund, A. M. (2023). Rule of Law Challenges of 'Algorithmic Discretion' & Automation in EU Border Control. *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 25(3), 249-274. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718166-12340152>
- Gonzalez, R. (2022). War Virtually: The Quest to Automate Conflict, Militarize Data, and Predict the Future. In *University of California Press*. University of California Press. <https://www.ucpress.edu/books/war-virtually/hardcover>
- How AI Is Transforming Border Defense*. (n.d.). <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/ResearchInsight/ai-impact-analysis-on-border-security-industry.asp>
- Mantelero, A., & Samantha Esposito, M. (2021). An evidence-based methodology for human rights impact assessment (HRIA) in the development of AI data-intensive systems. *ScienceDirect*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2021.105561>
- NeilWalker. (2024, October 7). *AI in Border Management: Implications and Future Challenges - Border Security Report*. Border Security Report. <https://www.border-security-report.com/ai-in-border-management-implications-and-future-challenges/>
- Paterson, M., & Paterson, M. (2025, February 8). The Evolution of State in Political Science: A Journey Through Time. *Political Science Connect - Leading Political Science Academic Journals*. <https://www.polisciconnect.com/the-evolution-of-state-in-political-science/>
- Schmid, S. (2025, July 11). AI for border control – a 'geopolitical innovation race' at the EU's external borders. *Oxford Law Blogs*. <https://blogs.law.ox.ac.uk/border-criminologies-blog/blog-post/2025/07/ai-border-control-geopolitical-innovation-race-eus>
- Tyler, H. (2022, February 2). *The Increasing Use of Artificial Intelligence in Border Zones Prompts*. migrationpolicy.org. <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/artificial-intelligence-border-zones-privacy>
- UNHCR - The UN Refugee Agency. (n.d.). *Data protection | UNHCR*. UNHCR. <https://www.unhcr.org/data-protection>
- Zureik, E., & Salter, M. B. (2005). *Global Surveillance and Policing: Borders, Security, Identity* Editors. In *Google Books*. Taylor & Francis. https://books.google.com.pk/books/about/Global_Surveillance_and_Policing.html?id=R5fiYP7ZXukC&redir_esc=y